

Two-Layered Model of blood flow through arterial catheterization with non-symmetric constriction

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ABSTRACT

In this paper flow of blood through a narrow catheterized artery with axially non-symmetrical stenosis has been investigated. Flowing blood has been represented by a two-layered model consisting of a core region of suspension of all the erythrocyte assumed to be a particle-fluid suspension (i.e., a suspension of all erythrocyte in plasma) and a peripheral layer of plasma (Newtonian fluid). The expression for the flow characteristics, namely the impedance, the wall shear stress, the shear stress at stenosis throat has been derived. The extensive quantitative analysis is performed through numerical computations of the desired quantities having rheological relevance through their graphical representations so as to validate the applicability of the present model.

Keywords: Haematocrit, impedance, shear stress, erythrocyte, plasma

INTRODUCTION

Constriction, medically called stenosis, is a term that describes narrowing of an artery due to the accumulation of cholesterol, fats and the abnormal growth of tissue. Stenosis most commonly occurs in the large distributing arteries such as the coronary artery, or in the large renal, cerebral, iliac or femoral arteries. A common cause of this constriction is a chronic disease process called atherosclerosis. In the region of narrowing arterial constriction, the flow accelerates and consequently the velocity gradient near the wall region is steeper due to the increased core velocity resulting in relatively large shear stress on the wall even for a mild stenosis [1]-[3]. It has been established that development of stenosis in early stage of the disease, is strongly related to the characteristics of the blood flow by Gidden [4].

A large number of theoretical and experimental efforts have been made in the literature to explain the blood flow behavior when it flows through the vessels of circulatory system of living beings. To account for the new evidences uncovered through the improved initial experimental theories of blood flow from the numerous relevant and important contributions of [5]-[9] and many others, mathematical modeling of blood flow has been subject to constant changes and modifications. These listed investigators have used single-phase homogeneous Newtonian viscous fluid, a classical approach that does not account for the presence of red cells in blood while flowing through the circulatory system. Taylor [10] reported that at high shear rates and in larger vessel, blood behaves like a Newtonian fluid. Young [11] has analyzed the effects of stenosis on flow characteristics of blood treating blood as Newtonian fluid. Although, this approach provides satisfactory tools to describe certain aspects of blood flow in

aorta and large arteries, it fails to give an adequate representation of flow field, especially in the vessels of small diameter (2400-8 μ m), Srivastava [12].

Blood viscosity depends on the haematocrit, i.e. the percentage volume of blood is occupied by red blood cells. The relative viscosity of blood increases when the value increases above 45% in vitro. But in vivo, in large vessels, increase in haematocrit causes significant increase in viscosity whereas in smaller vessels having a diameter of less than 100 μ m (arterioles, capillaries and venules) the viscosity change per unit change in haematocrit is much less than the wide-bore vessel. This is because the RBC is very deformable and can squeeze themselves and pass through the smaller vessels. So the net change in viscosity per unit change in haematocrit is significantly less in the body than it is in vitro. But when there is an enormous increase in the number of RBC (haematocrit above 50%), e.g. polycythemia vera, the blood viscosity becomes as great as 10 times of water and causes increase in resistance which increases the work of heart. In case of higher haematocrit there is more friction between successive layers of blood and this friction determines viscosity conversely in severe anemia, the peripheral resistance is decreased which is partly due to the decrease in viscosity. Cardiac output increases and as a result, the work of the heart also increases in anemia, Oka [13].

With the advent of the discovery that the hemodynamic factors play an important role in the genesis and the proliferation of stenosis has attracted the interest of early investigators to study the response of blood flow through stenotic lesions [14]-[17] have pointed out that blood being a

suspension of corpuscles, behave like a non-Newtonian fluid at low shear rates. In particular Hershey[18] and Huckaback [19] have shown that blood flowing through a tube of diameter less than 0.2mm and at low shear rates less than 20/s, behaves as a power law-fluid while Casson [20], Reiner [21] and Charm [22] have suggested that blood inhibits yield stress and behaves as a Casson model fluid at a shear rate equal to 0.1/s.

An examination of viscometric data [23]-[25] suggests that non-Newtonian behavior of blood increases rapidly, when haematocrit rises above 20%, possibly reaching a maximum at between 40-70%. Cokelet [17] and Thurston [26] have shown experimentally that for blood flowing through small vessels, there is cell-free plasma (Newtonian viscous fluid) layer and a core region of suspension of all the erythrocytes.

The flowing blood has been represented by a Newtonian, non-Newtonian, single or double-layered fluid by the investigators in the literature while discussing the flow through stenoses. It is well known that blood may be represented by a single-layered model in large vessel; however, the flow through the small arteries is known to be a two-layered. Bugliarello [27] and Cokelet [17] have shown experimentally that for blood flowing through small vessels, there is cell-free plasma (Newtonian viscous fluid) layer and a core region of suspension of all the erythrocytes. Srivastava [28] concluded that the significance of the peripheral layer increases with decreasing blood vessel diameter. A large number of theoretical and experimental efforts have been made in the literature to explain the blood flow behavior when it flows through the vessels of circulatory system of living being.

Catheter procedure can both diagnose and treat heart and blood vessel conditions. The catheter tool device are used to gather the information such as, assess the amount of blood flow through the heart and blood vessel, to measure blood pressure, to measure the amount of oxygen in the blood, assess the electrical system of heart (electrophysiology), close the holes in heart, treat abnormal heart rhythms with ablation procedures and intravascular ultrasound diagnosis. A catheter is made of polyester based thermoplastic polyurethane, medical grade polyvinyl chloride etc. For the purpose of flexibility PVC materials containing added plasticizers are used in catheter which enables them to move through the branches or curved paths of the circulatory system. Transducers attached to catheters are of many uses in clinical works and the techniques is used for measuring blood pressure or other mechanical properties in artery [29],[30]. Layek [31] considered a two-layered model of blood flow through a catheterized artery with axially variable peripheral layer thickness and variable blood viscosity at the wall.

An effort is made in present work to study the effects of a catheter on the flow characteristics taking into account that flowing blood is to be represented as a two-layered, a macroscopic two-phase (i.e., a suspension of erythrocytes in plasma) fluid in core and plasma in peripheral layer of with non-symmetric constriction model in arteries. The arterial wall segment is considered rigid as well as deformable. The wall in the vicinity of the stenosis is usually relatively rigid when

stenoses develop in human vasculature. To neglected the entrance, end and special wall effects, the artery length is assumed large enough as compared to its radius.

2. Formulation of the problem

In this paper the axisymmetric flow of blood through an inserted catheterized artery of circular cross-section having non-symmetrical stenosis specified at the position as Figure 1. is considered. Blood is assumed to be represented by a two-layered model consisting of a central layer of suspension of all the erythrocytes (i.e., suspension of red cells in plasma) of radius R_1 and a peripheral layer of plasma (a Newtonian fluid) of thickness $(R-R_1)$. The stenosis geometry and the shape of the central layer, assumed to be manifested in the arterial segment, are described [32] and [33] in Figures 1 and 2, respectively, as

Figure 1. The geometry of a non-symmetrical stenosis.

$$\frac{R(z), R_1(z)}{R_0} = (1, \alpha) - \Delta [L_0^{(n-1)} (z-d) - (z-d)^n]; d \leq z \leq d + L_0, \\ = (1, \alpha); \quad \text{otherwise} \quad (1)$$

where $(R(z), R_0)$ are the tube radius (with, without) stenosis, $n (\geq 2)$ is a parameter (called shape parameter) determining the stenosis shape (the symmetric stenosis occur when $n = 2$), L is tube length, L_0 is stenosis length and d indicate its location, α is the ratio of central core radius to tube radius in unobstructed region. The parameter is given by

$$\Delta = \frac{(\delta, \delta_1) n^{n/(n-1)}}{R_0 L_0^n (n-1)} \quad (2)$$

where δ are the maximum height of stenosis and bulging of interface at $z=d+L_0$ such that $\delta = \delta_1$.

Figure 2. The shape of the central layer

The equations describing the steady flow of a two-phase macroscopic model of blood may be expressed [12] and [34] as

$$(1-C)\rho_f \left\{ u_f \frac{\partial u_f}{\partial z} + v_f \frac{\partial u_f}{\partial r} \right\} - (1-C) \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + (1-C) \mu_s(C) \nabla^2 u_f + CS(u_p - u_f) \quad (3)$$

$$(1-C)\rho_f \left\{ u_f \frac{\partial v_f}{\partial z} + v_f \frac{\partial v_f}{\partial r} \right\} = -(1-C) \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + (1-C) \mu_s(C) (\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{r^2}) v_f + CS(v_p - v_f) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} [(1-C)v_f] + (1-C) \frac{v_f}{r} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [(1-C)u_f] = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\rho_p \left\{ u_p \frac{\partial u_p}{\partial z} + v_p \frac{\partial u_p}{\partial r} \right\} = -C \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + CS(u_f - u_p) \quad (6)$$

$$\rho_p \left\{ u_p \frac{\partial v_p}{\partial z} + v_p \frac{\partial v_p}{\partial r} \right\} = -C \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + CS(u_f - v_p) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} [C v_p] + \frac{C v_p}{r} - \frac{\partial [C u_p]}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (8)$$

with $\nabla^2 \equiv \partial^2/\partial r^2 + (1/r)(\partial/\partial r) + \partial^2/\partial z^2$ as a two-dimensional Laplacian operator, r is the radial coordinate measured perpendicular to the axis of tube. (u_f, v_f) and (u_p, v_p) are the (axial, radial) components of the fluid and particle velocities respectively, ρ_f and ρ_p are the actual density of the material constituting the fluid (plasma) and the particle (erythrocyte) phases respectively, $(1-C)\rho_f$ is the fluid phase and $C\rho_p$ is particle phase densities, C denotes the volume fraction density of the particles, p is the pressure, $\mu_s(C) \cong \mu_s$ is the mixture viscosity (apparent or effective viscosity), S is the drag coefficient of interaction for the force exerted by one phase on the other, and the subscripts f and p denote the quantities associated with the plasma (fluid) and erythrocyte (particle) phases, respectively. Other limitations of the present model are the same as discussed in [35]. The expressions for drag

coefficient of interaction, S and the viscosity of the suspension, μ_s for the present study are selected [22] and [35] as

$$S = \frac{9}{2} \frac{\mu_0}{a_0^2} \frac{4 + 3[8C - 3C^2]^{1/2} + 3C}{(2 - 3C)^2} \quad (9)$$

$$\mu_s(C) = \frac{\mu_0}{1 - mC} \quad (10)$$

$$m = 0.070 \exp[2.49C + (1107/T) \exp(-1.69C)] \quad (11)$$

where T is the measure in absolute scale of temperature (K), μ_0 is the constant plasma viscosity and a_0 is the radius of a red cell.

Now following the reports of Young [11] and Srivastava [34] the equations governing the laminar, steady, one-dimensional flow of blood in an artery in the case of a mild stenosis (i.e., $\delta/R_0 \ll 1$) are derived from equations (3) - (8) as

$$(1-C) \frac{dp}{dz} = (1-C) \frac{\mu_s(C)}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) u_f + CS(u_p - u_f), \quad R_c \leq r \leq R_1 \quad (12)$$

$$C \frac{dp}{dz} = CS(u_f - u_p), \quad R_c \leq r \leq R_1 \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dz} = \frac{\mu_0}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) u_0, \quad R_1 \leq r \leq R \quad (14)$$

Boundary conditions are,

$$u_0 = 0 \text{ at } r = R(z) \quad (15)$$

$$u_0 = u_f \text{ and } \tau_0 = \tau_f \text{ at } r = R_1 \quad (16)$$

$$u_f = 0 \text{ at } r = R_c \quad (17)$$

Analysis

Integration of Eqs. (12)-(14), subject to boundary conditions (15)-(17), yields the following expressions for the velocities u_0, u_f and u_p given as

$$u_0 = \frac{-R_0^2}{4\mu_0(1-C)} \frac{dp}{dz} \left[(1-C) \left\{ (R/R_0)^2 - (r/R_0)^2 \right\} + X \log(r/R) \right], \quad (18)$$

$$u_f = \frac{-R_0^2}{4\mu_0(1-C)} \frac{dp}{dz} \left[\mu \left\{ (R_c/R_0)^2 - (r/R_0)^2 \right\} + X \log(r/R_c) \right], \quad (19)$$

$$u_p = \frac{-R_0^2}{4\mu_0(1-C)} \frac{dp}{dz} \left[\mu \left\{ (R_c/R_0)^2 - (r/R_0)^2 \right\} + X \log(r/R) + \frac{4\mu_0(1-C)}{SR_0^2} \right], \quad (20)$$

Where $\mu = \frac{\mu_0}{\mu_s}$ and $X = \left[\frac{(1-C) \left\{ (R/R_0)^2 - (R_1/R_0)^2 \right\} - \mu \left\{ (R_c/R_0)^2 - (R_1/R_0)^2 \right\}}{\log(R/R_c)} \right]$.

The flow flux, Q is now calculated as

$$Q = 2\pi \left\{ \int_{R_1}^R r u_0 dr + \int_0^{R_1} r [(1-C)u_f + C u_p] dr \right\}$$

$$Q = \frac{-\pi R_0^4}{8\mu_0(1-C)} \frac{dp}{dz} \left[(1-C) \left\{ \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2 \right\}^2 + X \left\{ \left(\frac{R_c}{R_0} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{R}{R_0} \right)^2 \right\} \right] + 2X \frac{R_1^2}{R_0^2} \log \frac{R/R_0}{R_c/R_0}$$

$$- \mu \left\{ \left(\frac{R_c}{R_0} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2 \right\}^2 + \beta \left\{ \left(\frac{R_1}{R_0} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{R_c}{R_0} \right)^2 \right\} \right\}, \quad (21)$$

with $\beta = 8C(1-C)\mu_0 / SR_0^2$, a non-dimensional suspension parameter. The use of the fact that the total flux is equal to the sum of the fluxes across the two regions (peripheral and core) determines the relations $R_1 = \alpha R$ and $\delta_1 = \alpha \delta$. In view of these relation, the pressure drop, $\Delta p (= p$ at $z = 0$, $-p$ at $z = L$) across the stenosis between the sections $z = 0$ and $z = L$ is calculated from Eq. (21) as

$$\Delta p = \int_0^L \left(- \frac{dp}{dz} \right) dz = \frac{8(1-C)\mu_0 Q}{\pi R_0^4} \psi \quad (22)$$

$$\text{Where } \psi = \int_0^d [\phi(z)]_{R/R_0=1} dz + \int_d^{d+L_0} \phi(z) dz + \int_{d+L_0}^L [\phi(z)]_{R/R_0=1} dz$$

$$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{(1-C)\{(R/R_0)^2 - (R_1/R_0)^2\}^2 + X\{(R_c/R_0)^2 - (R/R_0)^2\} + 2X(R_1/R_0)^2}{\log \frac{R/R_0}{R_c/R_0} - \mu\{(R_c/R_0)^2 - (R_1/R_0)^2\} + \beta\{(R_1/R_0)^2 - (R_c/R_0)^2\}} \right]}$$

The first and third integral in the expression for ψ obtained above are straight forward whereas the evaluation of the second integral in closed form is formidable task and thus evaluated numerically. Following [34] one derives the expression for the impedance, λ , the wall shear stress τ_w , the shear stress at the stenosis throat, τ_s in their non dimensional form as

$$\lambda = (1-C) \left[\frac{(1-L_0/L)}{\eta} + \frac{1}{L} \int_d^{d+L_0} \phi(z) dz \right], \quad (23)$$

$$\tau_w = (1-C) (R/R_0) \phi(z), \quad (24)$$

$$\tau_s = (1-C) [(R/R_0) \phi(z)]_{R/R_0=1-\delta/R_0} \quad (25)$$

where, $\lambda = \bar{\lambda}/\lambda_0$, $(\tau_w, \tau_s) = (\bar{\tau}_w, \bar{\tau}_s)/\tau_0$, $\bar{\lambda} = \Delta p / Q$, λ_0 and τ_0 are the impedance and shear stress in normal (no stenosis) artery for a Newtonian fluid and $(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{\tau}_w, \bar{\tau}_s)$ are (impedance, wall shear stress, shear stress at the stenosis throat) in their non-dimensional form.

In absence of the catheter (i.e., under the limit $R_c/R_0 \rightarrow 0$), Eqs. (23)-(25) reduce to same result derived by Srivastava [36] for the case of a two-layered suspension blood flow as

$$\lambda_t = (1-C) \left[\frac{(1-L_0/L)}{(1-C)\{1 - (R_1/R_0)^4\} + \mu(R_1/R_0)^4 + \beta(R_1/R_0)^2} + \frac{1}{L} \int_d^{d+L_0} \frac{dz}{(1-C)\{(R/R_0)^4 - (R_1/R_0)^4\} + \mu(R_1/R_0)^4 + \beta(R_1/R_0)^2} \right], \quad (26)$$

$$\tau_{wt} = (1-C) \frac{(R/R_0)}{(1-C)\{(R/R_0)^4 - (R_1/R_0)^4\} + \mu\{(R_1/R_0)^2 + \beta\}(R_1/R_0)^2}, \quad (27)$$

$$\tau_{st} = (1-C) \frac{(1-\delta/R_0)}{(1-C)\{(1-\delta/R_0)^4 - (R_1/R_0)^4\} + \mu\{(R_1/R_0)^2 + \beta\}(R_1/R_0)^2}, \quad (28)$$

The subscript t denotes the quantities associated with a two layered suspension blood flow model. In addition, in absence of the peripheral layer (i.e., $\alpha = 1$), Eqs. (26)-(28) reduce to same

result derived by Srivastava [37] for the case of a single-layered macroscopic two-phase blood flow as

$$\lambda_m = (1-C) \left[\frac{(1-L_0/L)}{\mu + \beta} + \frac{1}{L} \int_d^{d+L_0} \frac{dz}{\mu(R/R_0)^4 + \beta(R/R_0)^2} \right], \quad (29)$$

$$\tau_{wm} = \frac{(1-C)}{\mu(R/R_0)^3 + \beta(R/R_0)}, \quad (30)$$

$$\tau_{sm} = \frac{(1-C)}{\mu(1-\delta/R_0)^3 + \beta(1-\delta/R_0)}, \quad (31)$$

The subscript m stands for the quantities associated with a single layered macroscopic two phase blood flow.

In addition, in absence of the erythrocyte phase (i.e., $C=0$), the Eqs. (29)-(31) reduce to same result derived by Young [11] and Srivastava [38] for the blood flow characteristics for a single-layered Newtonian fluid as

$$\lambda_n = 1 - \frac{L_0}{L} + \frac{1}{L} \int_d^{d+L_0} \frac{dz}{(R/R_0)^4}, \quad (32)$$

$$\tau_{wn} = \frac{1}{(R/R_0)^3}, \quad (33)$$

$$\tau_{sn} = \frac{1}{(1 - \delta/R_0)^3}, \quad (34)$$

The subscript n stands for the quantities associated with Newtonian fluid case.

Figure 3. Impedance, λ versus stenosis height, δ/R_0 for different catheter size, ε .

Numerical Result And Discussion

To have a quantitative estimate of the various parameters involved, computer codes are developed to evaluate the analytical result at a temperature of 37 in a tube of radius =0.1 and some critical result at are displayed graphically in fig. (3)-(10). In view of the fact that the peripheral layer thickness strongly depends on core suspension viscosity (i.e., on erythrocyte concentration; Bugliarello [27] and Srivastava [28] we choose $2a_0$ (erythrocyte diameter) = $8 \mu m$, the peripheral layer thickness, $\omega = \omega(C) = 6.18, 4.67, 3.60, 3.12, 2.58, 2.18$ corresponding to haematocrit, $C = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6$, respectively. The value of parameter is then calculated from the relation $\alpha = 1 - \omega/R_0$. The other parameter are selected as: $d(\text{cm})=0$; $L_0(\text{cm})=1$; $L(\text{cm})= 1, 2, 5$; catheter size $\varepsilon = R_c/R_0 = 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$. It is to note that the present analysis also corresponds the case of a Newtonian fluid through catheterized artery and no stenosis for parameter value $C=0$ and $\delta/R_0 = 0$, respectively.

The resistive impedance, λ increases with the stenosis height, δ/R_0 and increases with increasing value of catheter size, ε

for given haematocrit, C . However, the blood flow characteristics, λ decreases with increasing value of the shape parameter, n and attains its maximal magnitude in symmetric stenosis case ($n=2$) for given set of parameters fixed. One notices that the presence of the catheter causes significant increase in magnitude of the flow resistance (Figure 3).

The flow resistance, λ increases with stenosis height, δ/R_0 as well as with the haematocrit, C for given catheter size, ε (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Impedance, λ versus stenosis height, δ/R_0 for different haematocrit, C .

Figure 5. Impedance, λ versus catheter size, ε for different stenosis height, δ/R_0 and C .

The magnitude of flow resistance is higher in particle-fluid suspension than that in particle-free flow ($C=0$). For any given stenosis height, δ/R_0 the shape parameter, n and haematocrit, C the resistive impedance, λ steeply increases with catheter size, ε for small values but increases rapidly for high values and assumes very high asymptotic magnitude at about the half of catheter size, ε (Figure 5). Thus, the size of the catheter must be chosen keeping in view of the stenosis height during the medical treatment. And the magnitude of the flow

characteristics impedance, λ is higher in particle-fluid suspension than that of in particle-free flow ($C=0$). Also the magnitude of the flow characteristics impedance, λ is higher in arterial catheterization than those in artery without catheter $\varepsilon = 0$ (Figure 5).

The flow resistance, λ seems to be increasing steeply with haematocrit, C for any given catheter size, ε and stenosis height, δ/R_0 (Figure 6).

The blood flow characteristics, λ decreases with increasing tube length, which in terms implies that impedance, λ increases with increasing stenosis length L (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Impedance, λ versus haematocrit, C for different stenosis height, δ/R_0 .

Figure 7. Impedance, λ versus stenosis height, δ/R_0 for different catheter size, ε and length L .

The blood flow characteristics, λ decreases with increasing tube length, which in terms implies that impedance, λ increases with increasing stenosis length L (Figure 7).

The wall shear stress in the stenotic region, τ_w increases rapidly in upstream of the stenosis throat from its approached value (at $Z/L_0 = 0$) and achieve its maximal magnitude at stenosis throat ($Z/L_0 = 0.5, 0.6, 0.7$ for $n = 2, 6, 11$) then decreases rapidly in the downstream of throat to its approached value at end point of constriction profile (at $Z/L_0 = 1$) (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Wall shear stress distribution, τ_w in stenotic region for different catheter size, ε .

Figure 9. Wall shear stress distribution, τ_w in stenotic region for different haematocrit, C .

Figure 10. Wall shear stress at stenosis throat, τ_s versus stenosis height, δ/R_0 for different catheter size, ε .

The shear stress at stenosis throat, τ_s increases with stenosis height, δ/R_0 with haematocrit, C as well as with catheter size, ε (Figure 9, 10 and 11)

Figure 11. Wall shear stress at stenosis throat, τ_s versus catheter size, ϵ for different stenosis height, δ/R_0 .

Figure 12. Wall shear stress at stenosis throat, τ_s versus haematocrit, C for different stenosis height, δ/R_0 .

Concluding Remarks:

Stenosis, a constriction in blood vessels, is one of the leading causes of the death in the world. To estimate the flow characteristics through arterial catheterization with non-symmetric constriction, a two-layered model for blood has been considered. The impedance increases with the catheter size, the haematocrit and the stenosis height but decrease with shape parameter. Depending on the size of the stenosis, the flow resistance assumes a very high asymptotic magnitude with increasing catheter size. However study suggests that the catheter size should not exceed more than fifty percent of the artery size in any situation. Hence it should be noted that the catheter has a lot of impact on rheological properties of blood flow in arteries. The wall shear stress in the stenotic region increases in upstream of the stenosis throat but decreases in downstream of the throat and achieves to its approached value at a critical axial distance. The shear stress at stenosis throat possesses the characteristics similar to that of the flow resistance with respect to given parameter. The magnitude of the flow characteristics are higher in particle-fluid suspension than that of particle-free suspension ($C=0$).

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